

Impact of Bank of Agriculture Credit on Output of Rural Farmers in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study assessed the impact of Bank of Agriculture (BOA) credit on the productivity of rural farmers in the study area. A total of 500 respondents were surveyed, and descriptive statistics, t-tests, and multiple regression analyses were used. Findings reveal that 91.6% of respondents accessed agricultural microloans, while 6.8% and 1.2% accessed the Grow and Earn More and SME loans, respectively. The majority (64%) were charged 20% interest, and land (85.6%) was the dominant form of collateral. Results also show that BOA beneficiaries had significantly higher average labour use (85.35 vs. 36.25), income (₦944,465 vs. ₦260,438), and output (₦905,364 vs. ₦276,739) than non-beneficiaries, with all differences significant at the 1% level. Effect sizes (Eta^2) indicated strong practical impacts, especially on labour (0.373) and income (0.239). Regression results showed that in the double-log model the best fit with $R^2 = 0.656$ credit ($\beta = 0.121, p < 0.01$), farm size ($\beta = 0.115, p < 0.01$), and labour ($\beta = 0.339, p < 0.01$) significantly influenced output. Other inputs such as seeds and fertilizer were not statistically significant. The findings suggest that BOA credit improves output primarily through increased labour and land utilization. The study recommends scaling up credit access, strengthening extension services, and improving input quality and monitoring systems to enhance the productivity of rural farmers.

Keywords: BOA credit, farm output, rural farmers, agricultural productivity.

Introduction

In Nigeria, a large proportion of the population lives in rural areas where agriculture serves as the primary source of livelihood. Despite its significance, the rural economy is plagued by poverty, illiteracy, and low-income levels. The International Fund for

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INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Brainspec Publishers

VOLUME 3, ISSUE 3, AUGUST, 2025

ISSN: 3026-9733

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Agricultural Development (IFAD) has noted that about one-third of the world's poor live in rural areas and rely on agriculture. The Nigerian agricultural sector, though vital, faces challenges such as low productivity, poor infrastructure, climate vulnerabilities, and limited access to financial services. Migration of youths to urban centers in search of white-collar jobs has further reduced the rural workforce, worsening productivity and economic stagnation in these communities (Ethim & Udoh, 2018).

Access to credit is a major constraint to agricultural development and rural empowerment in Nigeria. Both IFAD and the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) have highlighted that rural areas receive less than 10% of official development assistance. Lack of credit has consistently hindered the ability of rural farmers to invest in improved production methods and technologies. Awoyemi et al. (2017) emphasized that the rural economy is trapped in a cycle of low investment, low income, and low productivity. Adetiloye (2012) and other scholars argue that access to credit is vital for poverty reduction and income improvement in rural areas. Given that agriculture contributes significantly to Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product (Olaniyi et al., 2015), providing credit to farmers is essential for boosting productivity and enhancing national food security.

Over the years, the Nigerian government has introduced several policies and institutions to improve credit access for rural farmers. These include Operation Feed the Nation (OFN), Agricultural Development Projects (ADPs), the Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme (ACGS), and the Nigerian Agricultural, Cooperative and Rural Development Bank (NACRDB), now rebranded as the Bank of Agriculture (BOA). Additionally, reforms such as the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) of 1986 deregulated the financial market, although with mixed outcomes. In 2006, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) introduced the National Microfinance Policy and later supported the Agricultural Credit Support Scheme (ACSS) to enhance credit access at affordable rates. Despite these initiatives, rural farmers continue to face barriers such as lack of collateral, high cost of borrowing, and inadequate infrastructure. To address the challenges in the sector, this study aims to assess the impact of Bank of Agriculture (BOA) credit on the output of rural farmers in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are to identify the types of credit disbursed to farmers by the Bank of Agriculture, Compare the effect size of BOA loan beneficiaries to non-beneficiaries and examine the effect of microcredit on farm output. This investigation is

crucial for understanding the role of BOA in rural agricultural financing and providing policy recommendations to improve its impact.

Literature Review

The literature review begins with a theoretical overview that lays the foundation for understanding agricultural credit within a broader economic context. Central to this section is the Risk and Uncertainty Theory of Agricultural Credit as conceptualized by Frank (1964), which underscores the inseparable link between agricultural credit availability and risks inherent in farming activities. Risks such as crop failure, natural disasters, and price volatility reduce creditworthiness and discourage lending. Avci (2020) expanded on these risks by highlighting financial losses faced by borrowers and the need for effective risk-mitigation strategies for both lenders and borrowers. Mechanisms such as improving income stability, ensuring timely borrowing and repayment, and linking credit with marketing institutions are advocated to enhance credit effectiveness and availability.

The review further discusses that for credit to be effective in boosting agricultural productivity, farmers must overcome psychological barriers such as the fear of debt. The review outlines key strategies to minimize lender risk and these include personal relationship building, supervision, reserve fund creation, and institutional linkages. Avci (2020) recommended strengthening farmers' risk-bearing capacity through crop diversification, insurance, and better planning. The theory concludes that credit should match the borrower's repayment ability to avoid financial collapse. Farm-level risk management should be context-specific, tailored by crop, farm size, or exposure to natural calamities.

In addition, the Demand and Supply Theory of Agricultural Credit by Oseni et al. (2020) explains the determinants of farmers' credit needs, including land size, farm productivity, technological adoption, and investment horizons. It highlights that poor farmers often avoid long-term investment due to limited resources and knowledge. However, modern agricultural practices are creating a rising demand for credit, especially for commercial and large-scale farming. Despite this, the supply of agricultural finance remains inadequate. The theory suggests that addressing financial bottlenecks through targeted policy interventions is crucial to bridging the gap between credit demand and supply in the agricultural sector.

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INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Brainspec Publishers

VOLUME 3, ISSUE 3, AUGUST, 2025

ISSN: 3026-9733

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Research Methodology

The study was carried out in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The state, rich in natural and human resources, especially in agriculture, provides an ideal setting for evaluating the impact of Bank of Agriculture (BOA) credit delivery. With its three senatorial districts (Uyo, Abak, and Oron), the study targeted rural farmers who either received or were denied microcredit from BOA, as the bank operates only in these three locations. These areas were selected for their accessibility and the presence of active agricultural activities influenced by government-backed microfinance initiatives since the early 2000s. A total of 510 respondents were selected using a convenience sampling technique, split equally between loan beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries across the three BOA branches. Of these, 500 properly completed questionnaires were used for the final analysis. A descriptive survey research design was employed, which allowed structured questionnaires to collect data on socio-economic characteristics, credit types, and credit usage. The survey method was justified due to its simplicity, clarity, and ability to capture real-time responses tailored to the study's objectives.

Table :1 Respondents number and location

Offices	Borrower	Non-Borrower	Total
Uyo	80	80	170
Abak	85	85	170
Oron	85	85	170
		Total	500

Data Analysis Techniques

A mix of descriptive and inferential statistics was used for data analysis. Descriptive statistics (frequencies, means, percentages) addressed objectives related to socio-economic profiles, credit types, usage, and constraints. The independent sample t-test and Eta-squared statistic were used to compare outputs between credit beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries. For assessing the impact of credit on income and productivity, multiple regression analysis was applied using Likert scale-transformed scores. Statistical tools such as SPSS and Excel facilitated the computation, allowing for robust interpretation of relationships between credit access and agricultural productivity.

Model Specification and Analytical Framework

The Cobb-Douglas production function was used to model the relationship between credit (as capital input) and farm output. The regression model incorporated variables such as farm size, seeds, fertilizers, and labor alongside credit. This functional form was chosen for its simplicity, ease of computation, and ability to interpret production elasticity. It allowed the researchers to determine how much variability in farm output could be explained by access to credit and other input factors, helping evaluate the impact of BOA interventions.

The regression line specified assumed a linear function. A linear function is a function that has the characteristic feature of equal variation. This implies that when the input variable is changed, the change in the output is expected to be proportional to the change in the input.

Douglas production function:

$$Q(L, K) = A * L^B * K^{and} \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation 1}$$

$$Y = f(X_i) \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation 2}$$

Where $i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$; while x represents the independent variables.

The regression line is specified below;

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \varepsilon \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation 3}$$

Where;

- Y= Farm Output (N)
- X_1 = Credit (N)
- X_2 = Farm size (ha)
- X_3 = Seeds (kg)
- X_4 = Fertilizer (kg)
- X_5 = Labour (man hour)
- β_0 = Regression intercept
- β_1 to β_5 = Regression coefficients
- ε = Error term.

Result and Discussions

Credit disbursed to farmers by BOA in the study area.

The result in Table 2 shows that the predominant credit facility disbursed by the Bank of Agriculture (BOA) in the study area is the Agricultural Microloan, accessed by 91.6% of the farmers. This overwhelming preference indicates BOA's strategic focus on supporting smallholder farmers through easily accessible microcredit, which often has fewer bureaucratic bottlenecks and lower capital requirements compared to larger loan schemes. A minimal percentage of farmers (6.8%) benefited from the Grow and Earn More loan, while only 1.2% accessed the SME Loan, showing limited diversification in loan products. This aligns with the findings of Oboh and Ekpebu (2011), who observed that microloans remain the dominant form of agricultural credit among rural farmers due to ease of access and lower collateral demand.

Regarding interest rates, the majority (64.0%) of respondents reported being charged 20% interest, while 31.2% paid 10% and only 4.8% were charged 12%. The high concentration of loans with a 20% interest rate suggests a potential disincentive for borrowers, especially for resource-poor farmers who may find such rates burdensome. Although microloans are meant to be more affordable, this data indicates that BOA's interest structure may still limit the full benefits of credit access. This supports empirical observations by Etonihu et al. (2013), who found that high interest rates from formal credit institutions can significantly erode the profitability of agricultural production, thereby discouraging further loan uptake and undermining rural financial inclusion efforts.

Collateral analysis revealed that 85.6% of respondents used land to secure loans, while 12.8% used houses. The reliance on land indicates that asset-based lending remains the dominant practice, which may exclude tenant farmers and landless agricultural workers from accessing credit. This supports the argument by Olagunju and Ajiboye (2010), who noted that land as collateral discriminates against vulnerable groups like women and young farmers, thereby limiting their participation in agricultural credit schemes. Moreover, the data suggests that BOA may not be fully implementing innovative collateral alternatives such as group guarantees or warehouse receipts, which have been recommended in rural finance literature to enhance inclusiveness.

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Brainspec Publishers

VOLUME 3, ISSUE 3, AUGUST, 2025

ISSN: 3026-9733

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Table 2: Types of credit disbursed to farmers by BOA in the study area.

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
<i>Credit Type</i>		
Agricultural Microloan	229	91.6
Grow and Earn More	17	6.8
SME Loan	3	1.2
No response	1	0.4
Total	250	100
<i>Interest Charged</i>		
10%	74	31.2
12%	12	4.8
20%	160	64.0
No response	4	1.6
Total	250	100
<i>Collateral used to access loans</i>		
Land	214	85.6
House	32	12.8
No response	4	1.6
Total	250	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Comparison of labor, income and output level of borrowing and non-borrowing farmers.

Table 3 reveals a significant difference in labor utilization between credit beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries. Beneficiary farmers used an average of 85.35 labor units compared to 36.25 for non-beneficiaries, with a highly significant *t-value* of 12.15 ($p <$

IJCITR

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0.01) and a large effect size ($\text{Eta}^2 = 0.373$). This implies that access to credit enables farmers to hire more labor, thereby expanding their farm operations and potentially improving efficiency. This finding is consistent with Onugu et al. (2017), who reported that farmers with access to formal credit services were more likely to employ hired labor, enhancing their productive capacity and timeliness of farming activities. The result also indicates a substantial income difference between the two groups. Beneficiaries earned a significantly higher average income of ₦944,465 compared to ₦260,438 for non-beneficiaries, with a *t-value* of 8.842 ($p < 0.01$) and an Eta^2 of 0.239, indicating a large effect size. This underscores the role of credit in boosting farm profitability by facilitating access to critical inputs, improved technology, and timely operations. Empirical studies such as Afolabi (2010) have affirmed that credit access significantly enhances the income-generating ability of smallholder farmers by reducing financial constraints and increasing farm investment. In terms of output, farmers who accessed credit achieved a mean output of ₦905,364 compared to ₦276,739 for non-beneficiaries. The difference is statistically significant ($t = 8.340, p < 0.01$), with an Eta^2 of 0.219, suggesting that credit significantly influences productivity. This supports the findings of Awotide et al. (2015), who observed that credit-constrained farmers tend to underproduce due to limited access to inputs, improved seeds, and fertilizers. Credit access not only increases the scale of production but also enhances the adoption of modern farming techniques, which can lead to yield improvements and better market competitiveness.

Table 3: Comparison of labor, income and output level of borrowing and non-borrowing farmers.

Variable	Farmers	Mean	SD	t	Df	Sig	Eta ²
Labour	Beneficiary	85.35	38.47	12.15***	324	0.00	0.373
	Non-Beneficiary	36.25	29.48				
Income	Beneficiary	944,465	562,508	8.842***	412	0.00	0.239
	Non-Beneficiary	260,438	906,888				
Output	Beneficiary	905,364	603,763	8.340***	437	0.00	0.219
	Non-Beneficiary	276,739	914,735				

Source: Computed from field survey data 2024 *** means significance at 1%, ** is significant at 5% while * is significance at 10%

Impact of BOA credit on farm output

The results of the multiple regression analysis presented in Table 4 reveal that Bank of Agriculture (BOA) credit has a statistically significant and positive impact on farm output in the study area. Among the four functional forms tested, the double-log model produced the best fit with an R^2 of 0.656 and an F-statistic of 6.138, both significant at the 1% level. In this model, the coefficient of credit (X_1) is 0.121 and is statistically significant at the 1% level, indicating that a 1% increase in credit access leads to an approximate 0.12% increase in farm output, holding other variables constant. This finding suggests that access to credit empowers farmers to invest in productivity-enhancing inputs, aligning with empirical evidence from *Oluwatayo and Adedeji (2019)*, who found that agricultural credit significantly boosts productivity and profitability among smallholder farmers in Nigeria. Furthermore, other explanatory variables such as farm size (X_2) and labor (X_5) also show significant positive effects on farm output in the double-log model. The farm size coefficient of 0.115 (significant at 1%) indicates that land expansion contributes meaningfully to increased output. Similarly, labor has a strong positive impact, with a coefficient of 0.339 (significant at 5%). These findings highlight the complementary role of credit, land, and labor in enhancing agricultural productivity. This is consistent with the work of *Adebayo and Adeola (2008)*, who observed that farm resources, particularly land and hired labor, interact with credit to significantly influence farm yield levels in rural Nigeria.

Interestingly, input variables such as seeds and fertilizer were not statistically significant across the models, suggesting possible inefficiencies or constraints in their usage despite credit availability. This might reflect poor input quality, inappropriate application, or limited access to extension services. The relatively high adjusted R^2 in the double-log (0.537) and linear (0.466) models affirms the overall reliability of the regression model in explaining variations in farm output. Therefore, the empirical results corroborate existing literature that access to agricultural credit, especially from institutions like BOA, significantly contributes to improved output when combined with other key resources, such as land and labor (*Oboh & Kushwaha, 2009*). This underlines the importance of designing integrated support systems beyond credit provision to optimize farm productivity.

Table 4: Result of Multiple Regression analysis

Variables	Linear	Semi-log	Double Log	Exponential
Constant	10.982 (2.836)***	22811.698 (0.267)	5.558 (2.599)***	1937.248 (0.018)
Credit (X1)	0.364 (2.220)**	2.602 (1.737)*	0.121 (2.908)***	0.143 (2.683)**
Farm Size (X2)	0.254 (2.203)**	0.427 (0.143)	0.115 (3.210)***	738.120 (1.052)
Seeds (X3)	1008.231 (0.339)	730.180 (0.174)	0.070 (0.703)	2256.601 (0.107)
Fertilizer (X4)	-0.854 (0.251)	0.113 (0.503)	0.087 (0.744)	-3859.726 (-0.145)
Labour (X5)	0.396 (1.662)**	0.164 (1.829)*	0.339 (2.637)**	-0.245 (2.115)**
R2	0.581	0.405	0.656	0.489
Adjusted R2	0.466	0.382	0.537	0.410
F- ratio (statistics)	3.480***	1.775*	6.138***	2.248**

Source: Computed from Field survey data, 2024

Conclusion and Recommendations

The findings from the regression analysis underscore the significant positive impact of BOA credit on farm output among rural farmers. In particular, credit, farm size, and labor were found to be statistically significant variables across several functional forms, with the double-log model producing the best fit ($R^2 = 0.656$). This suggests that farmers who accessed credit were more likely to expand their scale of production and invest in labor, leading to higher productivity. The positive and significant coefficients of credit confirm that BOA interventions in the form of financial support have effectively enhanced agricultural output. However, the non-significant effect of seeds and fertilizer indicates that access to inputs alone, without technical guidance or quality assurance, may limit the effectiveness of credit utilization. Based on these findings, it is recommended that BOA intensifies its credit delivery to farmers, ensuring the process is timely, accessible, and tailored to the farming season. To maximize the productivity impact of credit, extension services should be integrated into loan programs to educate farmers on effective input use and farm management practices. Additionally, the government should invest in land development and rural labor support initiatives to

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INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Brainspec Publishers

VOLUME 3, ISSUE 3, AUGUST, 2025

ISSN: 3026-9733

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complement credit use. Strengthening the agricultural input supply chain and monitoring credit utilization will also ensure that loans are used for productive purposes and that farmers derive maximum benefit from such interventions.

References

- Abdul-Rahman, S., & Abdulai, A. (2018). Impact of microcredit on farming productivity and welfare: Evidence from Northern Ghana. *World Development*, 102, 123–135. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2017.09.014>
- Adeniyi, A., & Ajayi, A. O. (2021). Access to agricultural credit and its impact on output among smallholder farmers in Nigeria. *Journal of Agricultural Finance and Rural Development*, 11(2), 45–54.
- Awotide, B. A., Abdoulaye, T., Alene, A., & Manyong, V. M. (2015). Impact of access to credit on agricultural productivity: Evidence from smallholder cassava farmers in Nigeria. *Journal of Agricultural and Applied Economics*, 47(2), 257–283. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1074070800006939>
- Bank of Agriculture (BOA). (2023). Annual Report and Financial Statement. Retrieved from <https://www.boanig.com>
- Bourdieu, P. (1986). The forms of capital. In J. G. Richardson (Ed.), *Handbook of Theory and Research for the Sociology of Education* (pp. 241–258). Greenwood.
- Nwaru, J. C. (2011). Determinants of informal credit demand and supply among food crop farmers in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Journal of Rural Economics and Development*, 20(1), 1–13.
- Oboh, V. U., & Ekpebu, I. D. (2011). Determinants of formal agricultural credit allocation to the farm sector by arable crop farmers in Benue State, Nigeria. *African Journal of Agricultural Research*, 6(1), 181–185. <https://doi.org/10.5897/AJAR.9000285>

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Brainspec Publishers

VOLUME 3, ISSUE 3, AUGUST, 2025

ISSN: 3026-9733

Adedeji, Gabriel Kolawole

- Odoemenem, I. U., & Obinne, C. P. O. (2010). Assessing the factors influencing the utilisation of formal credit among rural farmers in Benue State, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Economics and Financial Research*, 4(2), 35–42.
- Okurut, F. N., Banga, M., & Mukungu, A. (2004). *Microfinance and Poverty Reduction in Uganda: Achievements and Challenges*. Research Series No. 41. Economic Policy Research Centre.
- Yusuf, S. A., & Adedayo, A. (2012). Effect of microcredit on agricultural productivity of rural farm households in Ogun State, Nigeria. *World Rural Observations*, 4(1), 22–29.
- Avci, E. (2020). Risk and uncertainty in agricultural finance: Implications for credit access and management. *Journal of Agricultural Economics and Development*, 9(2), 33–45.
- Frank, R. (1964). Uncertainty and agricultural credit markets. *The Economic Journal*, 74(294), 302–312.
- Oseni, B., Yusuf, T., & Adegbite, A. (2020). Demand and supply dynamics of agricultural credit in developing economies: Evidence from Nigeria. *African Journal of Agricultural Economics and Rural Development*, 8(3), 44–58.